

First application

Reference No.

Chg. Page	Document No.	Sign.	Date
Developed	Gyrichidi N.		
Verified	Romanov A.M.		
Approved	Romanov M.P.		

Electrical connections schematic of the interface unit between ArduRover-compatible controller and Unitree Go1 robot

Lit.	Weight	Scale
Page 1	Pages 1	